

AN ADAPTIVE DISCRETE-SMEARED CRACK (A-DISC) MODEL FOR COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Failure of fibre-reinforced composite laminates often involves numerous interacting failure mechanisms, including matrix cracking, interfacial delamination and fibre breakage. In numerical modelling, the discrete crack model (DCM) and smeared crack model (SCM) are generally adopted. In principle, DCMs offer greatest fidelity to the mechanics of crack growth, including interactions between different failure modes. SCMs, on the other hand, treat diffused damage by effective reduction of the stiffness matrix through damage evolution laws. However, the homogenization of cracks does not permit modelling of strong discontinuities and delamination-matrix crack interactions. To preserve fidelity to the fracturing process while maintaining computational efficiency, an adaptive discrete-smeared crack (A-DiSC) model is presented. The DCM is used to model individual matrix cracks at initiation of damage and the initial stages of propagation. Subsequently, with increasing matrix cracks, adaptive transition from DCM to coupled DCM/SCM is performed. Some critical cracks are explicitly retained in the model while shorter non-critical ones are converted to dispersed damage based on the principle of energy equivalence. An example of the application of the proposed method is demonstrated by the modelling of the open-hole tension (OHT) test of composite laminates.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this paper, we propose an adaptive discrete-smeared crack (A-DiSC) method for modelling progressive damage in composite laminates (Figure 1). At the initial stages of damage (Figure 1a), the floating node method (FNM [1]), a discrete method previously developed for explicit representation of matrix cracks, is used in order to accurately place the initiation and propagation of cracks. At the interfaces between plies where the matrix cracks meet and possibly intersect, it is necessary to partition the cohesive elements (CEs) which model potential delamination at these interfaces. The partitioning is effected by employing recently formulated separable cohesive elements [2], which enable modelling of the interaction between matrix cracks and interfacial delamination. As damage progresses, regions of high matrix crack density are adaptively converted to smeared crack representation according to a transition criterion, resulting in an evolving coupled or mixed DCM/SCM model (Figure 1b). Not all cracked regions are necessarily converted to SCM, however. Some cracks may potentially grow and drive the progressive failure process and should therefore be retained in discrete form. Such “critical” cracks are identified based on their growth and length, and forms part of the transition criterion. The numerous non-critical cracks (i.e. not deemed to be growing as rapidly) are converted into bulk damage representation (SCM) through a weak form of energy equivalence. Such a hybrid formulation of DCM and SCM enables both macroscopic crack propagation as well as diffused damage to be more accurately modelled and is more reflective of the state of damage in composite structures. The A-DiSC approach may also potentially reduce overall model size through modelling large regions of diffused damage through smeared properties, thereby providing an efficient pathway to model progressive damage in large composite engineering structures.

Figure 1 Conceptual illustration of the adaptive discrete-smeared crack (A-DiSC) model.

2 ADAPTIVE DISCRETE-SMEARED CRACK MODEL

In this section, the weak form of the thermodynamic equivalence between discrete and smeared crack approaches is derived in the context of matrix damage. When transiting from DCM to SCM, energetic equivalency should be enforced. To ensure global equilibrium, the stored free energy should be preserved in both models before and after the transition. Also, to avoid spurious self-healing or energy loss in the material, the available fracture energy to be transferred to SCM should be equal to the residual energy remaining in DCM.

2.1 Free energy

Figure 2 From discrete crack model (DCM) to smeared crack model (SCM).

The free energy stored in the DCM, Ψ_{DC} , consists two parts (Figure 2), the volume energy Ψ_{vol} contributed by two cracked linear elastic solids (green coloured) and the surface energy Ψ_s stored in fracture surfaces (grey coloured), respectively:

$$\Psi_{DC} = \Psi_{vol} + \Psi_s = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} dV + \int_S \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS. \quad (1)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}$ is the strain tensor and \mathbf{C} is the stiffness tensor for intact solids. $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ and $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ are interface traction and separation vectors, respectively. In the SCM, the free energy Ψ_{SC} is the energy stored in the damaged solids,

$$\Psi_{SC} = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} : \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} dV. \quad (2)$$

with $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ denoting the effective strain tensor and $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ is degraded stiffness tensor of the damaged materials (Figure 2). The displacements of eight corners (marked by \bullet in Figure 2) are mapped from the full DCM to SCM, such that effective strain $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}}$ of SCM is obtained accordingly.

When the transition is effected, the free energy is set to be equal, $\Psi_{DC} = \Psi_{SC}$, which is:

$$\int_V \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\epsilon} : \mathbf{C} : \boldsymbol{\epsilon} dV + \int_S \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS = \int_V \frac{1}{2} \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} : \tilde{\mathbf{C}} : \tilde{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} dV. \quad (3)$$

Provided the left-hand side of Eq. (3) can be evaluated for DCM, the solution of Eq. (3) at transition yields the damage variable $D_{m_1,ts}$ and the degraded elastic tensor $\tilde{\mathbf{C}}$ for SCM.

2.2 Equivalence of fracture energy

Figure 3 Equivalence of fracture energy between discrete crack model (DCM) and smeared crack model (SCM).

As shown in Figure 3, the total energy dissipated Φ_{DC} by a propagating crack is defined as,

$$\Phi_{DC} = \int_{S_c} \int_{D^{\Gamma}=0}^{D^{\Gamma}=1} d\mathfrak{D}^{\Gamma} dS_c = \int_{S_c} \int_0^{\delta_{e,f}} \tau_e d\delta_e dS_c = G_{e,m}^c A_c. \quad (4)$$

where S_c is the crack surface and A_c is the corresponding area. $G_{e,m}^c$ is the matrix fracture toughness, assumed constant during crack propagation. Suppose the transition occurs when damage variable $D^{\Gamma} = D_{ts}^{\Gamma}$, the remaining fracture energy to be transferred to the SCM is calculated as,

$$\begin{aligned} \Phi_{SC} &= \Phi_{DC} - \int_{S_c} \int_0^{D_{ts}^{\Gamma}} d\mathfrak{D}^{\Gamma} dS_c \\ &= \int_V \int_{D_{m_1,ts}}^1 d\mathfrak{D}^{\Omega} dV. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

When the transition is performed, $D_{m_1,ts}$ and Φ_{SC} are first calculated from Eqs. (3) and (5), and the cohesive law for SCM is formulated based on these two parameters. In this way, the energetic equivalence between DCM and SCM is achieved.

2.3 Transition of the cohesive interface

In addition to matrix cracking and fibre breakage discussed above, interfacial delamination is also a crucial mode of progressive damage in composite laminates. The potential smearing of cracks of adjacent plies (Figure 4) requires an equivalent strategy for the connecting CE. As shown in Figure 4a, the separable CE can be partitioned into several sub-elements according to the matrix crack configurations in neighbouring plies, correctly capturing the stress concentration and load transfer at the cohesive interface. Conversely, with discrete cracks smeared into volumetric damage, transition of the partitioned interfaces into equivalent unpartitioned ones must also be considered to enforce kinematic compatibility (Figure 4a-c).

Following the same approach of Section 2.1 and 2.2, energy equivalence is achieved when transition of the interface is effected. With reference to Figure 4, the balance of free energy is given as:

$$\underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^6 \left(\int_{S_c} \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS_c \right)_j}_{\text{Before transition}} = \underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^6 \left(\int_{S_c} \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS_c \right)_j}_{\text{After transition}}; \quad (6)$$

or

$$\underbrace{\sum_{j=1}^6 \left(\int_{S_c} \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS_c \right)_j}_{\text{Before transition}} = \underbrace{\int_{S_c} \frac{1}{2} \boldsymbol{\tau} \cdot \boldsymbol{\delta} dS_c}_{\text{After transition}}. \quad (7)$$

Here, j counts the sub-domains of the partitioned interface and it is assumed that damage is evenly distributed in the interface after the transition (same damage variable is assumed for the CEs after transition). Furthermore, the total energy to be dissipated by the interface is given as:

$$\Phi_I = \sum_{j=1}^6 \left(\int_{S_c} \int_{D^{\Gamma}=0}^{D^{\Gamma}=1} d\mathfrak{D}^{\Gamma} dS_c \right)_j = \sum_{j=1}^6 (G_{e,i}^c A_c)_j, \quad (8)$$

with $G_{e,i}^c$ the fracture toughness of the interface. With transition, the residual fracture energy Φ_R is calculated through:

$$\Phi_R = \Phi_I - \sum_{j=1}^6 \left(\int_{S_c} \int_0^{D_{ts}^{\Gamma}} d\mathfrak{D}^{\Gamma} dS_c \right)_j. \quad (9)$$

The residual energy is averaged and dissipated by the converted interface CEs.

The damage variable D^{Γ} for each interface CE is obtained through Eq. (6), and together with the residual energy Φ_R calculated from Eq. (9), the cohesive law for subsequent damage is determined.

Figure 4 Separable cohesive element: (a) element configurations with top and bottom cracks; (b) converted cohesive element with bottom crack smeared; (c) converted cohesive element with both top and bottom cracks smeared.

2.4 Transition criteria

In the proposed A-DiSC model, a key consideration is the criteria for transitioning from full DCM to coupled DCM/SCM. In this paper, we trigger the transition when: (a) the crack density in a composite ply reaches a pre-determined saturation, dictated by practical consideration of local mesh density or element size, and (b) retention of a finite number of critical matrix cracks in their discrete form, based on a minimum critical crack length. The implementation of this strategy is illustrated by the following example.

3 OPEN-HOLE TENSION (OHT) TEST

The A-DiSC model is demonstrated through the analysis of an OHT test of an IM7/8552 $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate [3]. Experimental studies [3] found that the failure of OHT $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminates was primarily dominated by delamination, in which extensive interfacial damage occurred between blocked plies of dissimilar fibre orientations. In particular, the widespread delamination at the $-45^\circ/0^\circ$ interface led to the distinctive load-drop and loss of structural stiffness.

3.1 Finite element model

Figure 5 Boundary conditions and FE mesh for OHT simulation of $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate [3].

Properties	Values
Longitudinal Young's modulus: E_1 (GPa)	161
Transverse Young's modulus: E_2, E_3 (GPa)	11.4
Shear modulus: G_{12}, G_{13} (GPa)	5.17
Shear modulus: G_{23} (GPa)	3.98
Poisson's ratio: ν_{12}, ν_{13}	0.32
Poisson's ratio: ν_{23}	0.43
Longitudinal tensile strength: X_t (MPa)	2806
Transverse tensile strength: Y_t (MPa)	60
Shear strength: S_t, S_l (MPa)	90
Interfacial normal strength: τ_{nc} (MPa)	40
Interfacial shear strength: τ_{tc}, τ_{lc} (MPa)	60
Mode I matrix fracture toughness: G_{nc} (kJ/m ²)	0.293
Mode II matrix fracture toughness: G_{tc}, G_{lc} (kJ/m ²)	0.631
Power-law exponent for mixed-mode fracture: α	1
Penalty stiffness (N/mm ³)	10^5

Table 1 Material properties of IM7/8552 composite laminate.

The geometry and boundary conditions of the OHT $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate are shown in Figure 5. For each of the fibre angles, there are four blocked plies and these are modelled by a single solid element in the thickness direction. CEs are pre-defined between ply elements to model potential delamination failure. Only half of the laminate in the thickness direction is modelled due to symmetry

about the mid-plane of the plate. The mesh consists of elements of about $0.2 \text{ mm} \times 0.2 \text{ mm}$ in dimension. Three models, i.e. the DCM, SCM and A-DiSC model, are analysed. The transition scheme and criteria for A-DiSC model are implemented at the ply level. The material properties of IM7/8552 composite are listed in Table 1. As recommended by van der Meer *et al.* [4] and Lu *et al.* [5], reduced interfacial normal and shear strengths are adopted.

3.2 Numerical predictions

Figure 6 Predicted matrix failure patterns from different models and experimental results.

The predicted matrix failure patterns from DCM, SCM and A-DiSC model are compared to experiment results, as shown in Figure 6. An extensive network of distributed matrix cracks is observed in DCM after the load-drop. For SCM, however, the predicted matrix failure patterns are significantly influenced by the mesh design and matrix cracks in the $\pm 45^\circ$ and 0° plies are not accurately modelled.

For failure analysis with A-DiSC model, adaptive transition scheme takes effect when matrix crack density saturates in the 90° and -45° plies. In the surface 45° and middle 0° plies, only a limited number of matrix cracks are predicted, so that DCM alone is sufficient. While the preserved critical cracks propagate significantly across the laminate, the diffused failure may evolve concurrently in the damaged region, showing a multi-scale damage process. Compared to the full DCM and SCM, the A-DiSC model enables an integrated representation of both discrete and smeared damage in a single analysis, which is closer to experiment observations.

Figure 7 Predicted load-displacement curves and experimental result [3, 6].

The predicted load-displacement curves and experimental result from literature [3, 6] are plotted in Figure 7. Good agreement is generally obtained from all three models, and the load-drop, due to significant delamination propagation at the $-45^\circ/0^\circ$ interface, is well captured. However, the SCM is unable to accurately model the interaction between matrix cracking and delamination, leading to delayed delamination failure and resulting in a higher predicted failure load. The DCM is unable to accurately describe the dispersive matrix damage due to the necessary constraint on finite crack spacing, hence also resulting in higher predicted failure load. In contrast, A-DiSC model is able to model at least the delamination and critical matrix crack interactions while allowing the diffuse matrix damage between discrete cracks to develop, leading to a lower prediction of failure load. The SCM failed to converge (at displacement of 0.39 mm) due to severe damage localisation and element distortion from material softening [7, 8]. Equilibrium was difficult to achieve with the standard implicit solver and successive cutbacks on time increment were necessary, which eventually led to abortion of the analysis. The A-DiSC model, on the other hand, successfully achieved convergence.

Models	DoFs	Iterations	CPU time (s)
Smeared crack model (SCM)	412704	N.A.	N.A.
Discrete crack model (DCM)	705012	4089	1066660
A-DiSC model	446202	3726	825149

*Due to the convergence problem, iteration number and CPU time are not available (N.A.) for SCM.

Table 2 Simulation details of different models for OHT test at final failure.

*Due to the convergence problem, iteration number and CPU time are not available (N.A.) for SCM.

Table 22 shows the comparison (at final separation failure) between the models for total degrees of freedom (DoFs), iterations and CPU time. The total DoFs remain constant throughout the analysis for SCM, but increase for DCM and A-DiSC as floating nodes are activated with progressive damage. Compared to DCM, up to 36.7% saving in total number of DoFs and 22.6% saving in CPU time are achieved with A-DiSC for the OHT problem analysed here.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, an adaptive discrete-smeared crack (A-DiSC) model is developed for the analysis of progressive failure of composite laminates. The energy equivalence between discrete crack model (DCM) and smeared crack model (SCM) as well as a transition strategy from DCM to SCM have been proposed. The A-DiSC model with coupled discrete and smeared crack representations is developed.

The performance of the proposed A-DiSC model is demonstrated through the example of the open-hole tension (OHT) test of a $[45_4/90_4/-45_4/0_4]_s$ laminate. The predictions of the A-DiSC model compares well with experimental observations of the multi-scale fracture and delamination patterns. Significant savings in computational time and model size are realized. The simulated delamination patterns and failure load also exhibit good correlation with experiment results.

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